

RELEASING ACCOUNTING INFORMATION AND ITS EFFECTS ON STOCK PRICES

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June, 2022

Abstract

An investor's primary objective is to make a fortune on stock trading. Making a fortune depends on a good understanding of the prices of stock of companies in which investors intend to invest in. The usefulness of accounting information is indicated by the ability of the information in the financial statements to shed light of stock measures. Efficient stocks spur a country's economic growth and development and stock markets serve to enhance private capital and facilitate capital market improvement. Reliable accounting information is therefore crucial for stock market growth as investors need adequate information so as to make informed investment decisions. Accounting information strongly impacts the volatility of stock process, and for this reason, managers must properly prepare and present accounting information to allow potential investors make economic and investment decisions to reduce stock price volatility. Many companies have undergone very turbulent times in their growth history attributable to crumbling investor interests in companies with volatile stock prices. This paper examines the impact of releasing accounting information and its effects on stock prices of a select listed company on the Australian stock exchange market (asx).

Releasing accounting information and its effects on stock prices

Price volatility can be defined as the dispersion measure around the mean return of a security or a range measure of the price of an asset about the mean level over a specified period. The price of stock is volatile when there will be a systemic mean variance over time period.

Less volatile stocks experience little change of prices over a specified time period (Jordan, 2014). Good understanding of stock prices determines the possibility of making fortunes in companies where investors intend to invest in. The value of accounting information is indicated by the ability of the information in the financial statements to reflect stock measures. Efficient stocks encourage a country's economic growth and development. On the other hand, stock markets enhance private capital and facilitate capital market improvement. Dependable and consistent accounting information is crucial for the growth of stock markets since investors rely on adequate information in making informed investment decisions. Accounting information has strong effects on volatility of stock process. Company managers, in response to this, prepare accounting information to enable potential investors make economic and investment decisions to lessen the volatility of stocks. Many companies have undergone very turbulent times in the history of their growth and this is related to collapsing investor interests.

A number of factors along with accounting information, such as financial policy, industrial policy, expectations of investors, market supervision, foreign trade policy and internal factors can bring about a change in the price of stock. Among all the listed factors, accounting information stands out as the most important one used by investors to make investment decisions based on the company stock as the price of stock of a company reflects the future profit. An investor will only analyze the information contained in the financial statements when evaluating the price of stocks of a company on bourse only if it furnishes them with the useful information. Due to this, accounting information must possess two qualitative features such as relevance and reliability for it to be useful and acceptable to potential investors(Frankel and Laby, 2015). If one or none of the qualities are present in an accounting statement and information, it will be

considered redundant. One of the most important objectives of financial reporting is provision of relevant information to equity investors for estimation of the value of a company.

Contrastingly, the determination of the prices of shares in the capital markets is affected by such factors as accounting and non-accounting information. Accounting information refers to the means of measuring and communicating economic events in business management, investment making and observation of receipt and disbursement of funds. This starts in the ratio form such as net assets per share, earnings per share, dividend cover, dividend per share, and book value per share. Non-accounting information, referred to information outside accounting such as speculation, rumors and gambling. The prices of stock are the basis of company valuation on whether it is breaking even or not and return measurement that accrues to stakeholders making their value a huge boost to existing and prospective investors in the capital markets.

Company managements release financial information as a way of communicating with stakeholders and the information released is a great guide to potential and existing investors. Information content of financial statements in efficient market hypothesis make available information to which the market can quickly react and have impacts on the prices of stock. Financial statements give a precise prediction and indication on the response of the market and this response is seen in the form of returns. In Australia, it is a lawful requirement that listed companies publish their financial and audit reports after every financial period. Stock returns are measured in terms of losses and gains on security from investment. Higher demand for stocks results in the rise of its value. Return on stocks is based on price rise from the par value and any dividend paid share price is determined by the future dividends of a company. The growth of a company is tied to a constant growth of dividends paid to its shareholders. Stock returns depend

on the financial performance of a company. The financial performance fluctuates based on internal and external factors. Financial information with negative impression results in a drop in investor interests to the company and this will be seen the fall of stock price hence affecting stock returns. It also results in no dividends lowering the share price and capital gains. Investors pay a great attention to the financial reports information signal.

A significant number of investors are irrational and have biases that cost them significant returns over the course of time. These biases include loss aversion, overconfidence and bandwagon. It is important that biases are managed to improve the performance of investments. These biases allow investors to heavily rely on past returns in making their investment decisions. Other risk biases that investors might encounter include non-reporting bias risk and instant history risk. For the survival of investments, investors need to acquire an informed oversight on the market either practically or by the use of financial managers who are informed and trained in investment management.

Investors seeking to improve their returns look out for stocks that have been mispriced. Mispricing can be both advantageous and disadvantageous to investors in that, underpricing of companies creates opportunities for investors whereas overpricing creates short opportunities. Most investors are not aware of mispricing as they believe in the efficient market hypothesis that assumes that market prices reflect all uniform available information relating to stock. A market can be pushed in a bull or bear run making it hard for investors to recognize peaks and troughs in an economic cycle (Carnall, 2018). This can also result in overlooking of company information by the market. Financial managers are very important and informed in recognizing mispricing and correction patterns and can help investors make informed investment decisions or make the

decisions on behalf of the investors with a view of protecting them from losses that could be related to their biases.

Biased investors have very minimal chances of survival since their investment decisions are not entirely based on financial facts and prognosis but on biases that are in no way related to the condition of the market, new opportunities and the running of the companies that they are poised to invest in (Carnall, 2018). The CEOs of companies to be invested in are professionals that are capable of making wise decisions that will affect the performance of companies. Even so, the financial performance trends of companies should be assessed by money managers to ensure that investors' monies are in the growing path by avoiding mispricing and correction patters that could be managed by CEO's to create an inaccurate impression. Money managers are therefore in a position to even make markets efficient since they play oversight roles in the performance of companies and advice their clients against companies that do not perform efficiently. Financial managers are very essential in the market in helping investors make informed decisions.

Data Analysis

Standard Chartered Bank

Days from release day	Share prices	ASX Index	MR (points)
30	219	4033	6.2
25	220	4039	3.9
20	221	3878	-2
15	213	4,001	4.9

10	215	3972	-7
5	217	3944	-1
0	214	3931	3.5

Markets are efficient when the prices of shares absorb all the information related to the market such as the current, historical and expected information and as a result, investors are not expected to earn abnormal returns. Models of markets are used in the determination of abnormal returns and cumulative abnormal returns at a study period. Abnormal returns are derived from the difference between the actual returns and the expected returns.

Graph: Average AR of Standard Chartered Bank

The figure above shows statistical evidence on the relationship between the release of information and share prices as well as abnormal returns. The efficient market theory states that

no player is able to obtain abnormal returns in a strong form market and the factors of stock prices in market information. The objective of the statistical test is to establish a correlation between the release of financial statements and the stock return. From the results, a rise in share price results in abnormal returns positing a substantive positive correlation between the release of financial information and return on stock s at the a period of announcement.

References

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